

Associations between vulnerability status, psychological stress, and suicidal ideation among adolescent girls and young women in Nigeria during the COVID 19 pandemic

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19665257>

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Abstract

Aim: This study assessed the risk for psychological stress and suicidal ideation among adolescent girls and young women vulnerable to HIV infection or living with HIV resident in Nigeria during the COVID 19 pandemic.

Methods: This was a secondary analysis of the data of adolescent girls and young women 15-24 years old recruited from 10 states distributed across the six geopolitical zones in Nigeria collected between the 30th of June and 1st of October 2021. The dependent variables were psychological stress and suicidal ideation. The independent variables were the social vulnerability status of the study participants (people with disabilities, sell sex, on the move use psychoactive substances, engage in transactional sex) and HIV status (negative, positive don't know/won't say). The confounding variables were sociodemographic variables (age, educational status, and socioeconomic standing). Two multivariable logistic regression analysis was done to determine the associations between the two dependent variables and independent variables after adjusting for confounders.

Results: People with disability (AOR:2.06), who used psychoactive substances (AOR:1.89), who sell sex (AOR:1.58) and living with HIV when compared with HIV negative status (AOR:2.04) had significantly higher odds of having psychological distress. Respondents who used psychoactive (AOR:1.44), sell sex (AOR:1.50), involved in transactional sex (AOR:1.45) and who reported "don't know" or "won't say" for their HIV status when compared with HIV negative individuals (AOR:1.57) had significantly higher odds of suicidal ideation.

Conclusion: The likelihood of risk of vulnerable adolescent girls and young women to psychological stress and suicidal ideation during the COVID-19 pandemic seem to differ for each sub-population. Vulnerability status may not be the only risk pathway for psychological stress and suicidal ideation in the sub-populations. Further studies are needed to understand the drivers of mental health challenges among adolescent girls and young women.

Key words:

Introduction

COVID-19 is associated with psychological stress. The prevalence of psychological distress (during the pandemic?) ranged between 18.1%–45.2% among the general population [1] with an increase of about 8% in self-report stress [2]. The fear of having COVID-19, poor access to healthcare, financial vulnerability, housing and food insecurity, isolation, lack of social contacts and fear of the unknown all contributed to the experience of psychological stress [3, 4]. Other causes include anger, anxiety, fear, depression, and insomnia [5]. The COVID-19 pandemic was also associated with suicidal ideation. The pooled prevalence of suicidal ideation resulting from the pandemic was 12.1%; a prevalence that was higher than that in the general population prior to the pandemic [6]. The main risk factors were poor access to social support, high physical and mental exhaustion sleep disturbances, quarantine and exhaustion, loneliness, and mental health difficulties [ditto]. The risk for suicidality during the pandemic is increased in persons who are exposed to COVID-19 stressors and psychological stress [7].

In Nigeria, the pandemic was associated with an increase in the risk of exposure to identified risk factors for psychological stress and suicidal ideation. These include fear, anxiety, depression and changes in sleep patterns [8]. Also, COVID-19 related fear, anger and loneliness were also expressed and associated with the use of reactive coping strategies [9]. The access to healthcare was poor [10], and access to essential health services was poorer for populations of girls and women with high risk for HIV infection or living with HIV [11]. Similarly, the experience of financial vulnerability, housing and food insecurity was worse for population of vulnerable girls and women [12]. Isolation, quarantine, and social distancing were instituted public health measures to contain the pandemic [13]; and the measures were associated with psychological distress [14]. The prevalence of COVID-19 psychological stress in the general population in Nigeria was xxx [15] and associated with higher risk for anxiety and depressive symptoms [14]. The prevalence of COVID-19 associated suicidal ideation in Nigeria was also estimated to be 3.8% [16, 17]. The prevalence of psychological stress and suicidal ideation among populations highly vulnerable to mental health challenges in Nigeria like females [18], and females living with HIV [19, 20] is unknown.

The aim of this research was to identify risk indicators for psychological distress and suicidal ideation among vulnerable adolescent girls and young women, living with and without HIV in Nigeria [11]. Mental health is a significant concern for adolescents and young adults, as it impacts various aspects of their lives, including school and work performance, relationships with friends and family, and community involvement [21, 22]. Furthermore, psychological stress is a known risk factor for suicidal ideation [24, 25]. In Nigeria, one in six individuals aged 15-24 suffers from poor mental health [26]. The prevalence of depressive symptoms (55.4%), high general anxiety (27.1%), and suicidal ideation (24.8%) among adolescents is alarmingly high [27]. Moreover, the COVID-19 pandemic has exacerbated mental health challenges for this age group [28]. By understanding the risk indicators, targeted interventions can be developed to support the mental wellbeing of adolescent girls and young women in Nigeria.

The study was guided by a conceptual framework that highlights how vulnerability to stress has a bidirectional relationship with mental health disorder like psychological stress and suicidal ideation [29]. HIV vulnerability status increases the risk for stress [30, 31]. Chronic stress, amplified by exposure to COVID-19, lead to the impairment of neuronal functions and other regulatory systems that maintain allostasis or psychological and physical balance [32, 33], overload one's coping capacity, decrease the quality of life and cause mental health morbidities [34, 35]. We postulate that girls and women at risk of or living with HIV live with chronic stress which was amplified by the COVID-19 pandemic due to problems like financial vulnerability, food and financial insecurity, social isolation, loneliness fear of contracting COVID-19, anxiety and depression [12, 36-38]. These increased the risk for COVID-19 related psychological stress and suicidal ideation. This study assessed the risk for psychological stress and suicidal ideation among adolescent girls and young women vulnerable to HIV infection or living with HIV resident in Nigeria during the COVID 19 pandemic. We hypothesis that adolescent girls and young women vulnerable to HIV infection or living with HIV resident in Nigeria are more likely to experience psychological stress and suicidal ideation during the COVID 19 pandemic.

Methods

Ethical considerations

Ethical clearance for the study was obtained from the institute of Public Health Research Ethics Committees (IPH/OAU/12/1692), Adamawa State (ADHEC07/06/2021), Anambra State

(MH/AWK/M/321/363), Akwa Ibom State (MH/PRS/99/Vol.V/994), Benue State (MOH/STA/208/Vol.1/183), Kaduna State (MOD/ADM/774/Vol.1/1008) and Lagos State (LS/C.350/S.1/215). Data were collected anonymously, confidentiality and privacy were ensured, and the rights and welfare of the research participants were safeguarded through measures taken to prevent the unintended collection of IP addresses. Participants provided written informed consent by ticking a checkbox before starting the online questionnaire. Study participants also had access to airtime vouchers of 1 000 naira (\approx USD 1.70) for data or internet usage.

Study design, study sites and study population

This was a secondary analysis of a cross-sectional study that generated information from participants resident in 10 states spread across the six geopolitical zones in Nigeria. The states were Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Benue, Kaduna, Lagos, Enugu, Nasarawa, Gombe and Niger states. Data were collected between the 30th of June and 1st of October 2021.

Study participants were adolescent girls and women, with intentional recruitment of women with disabilities (i.e. long-term physical or sensory impairments), women who sell sex (women engaging in commercial sex work), women on the move (migrants, refugees, asylum seekers, returning migrants and displaced persons), women who use psychoactive substances (women injecting or using illegal drugs), women who engage in transactional sex (women entering into a sexual relationship with a man – not a husband or partner – to obtain necessities such as food, clothing, school fees and gifts) and transgender women. Study participants had to be 15 years and older, identify as members of the target community and consent to study participation. There were no exclusion criteria. Details about the study methodology had been described in previous publications [11, 12, 39]. For this study, the data of adolescents and young women 15 to 24 years were extracted for analysis.

Sample size

The sample size for the primary study was pre-determined to recruit a minimum of 60 valid respondents per target population group in six states, corresponding to a minimum sample size of 2,160 participants. For this study, the minimum sample of 1509 respondents extracted allowed for statistical modelling since we had a minimum of 10 participants with complete responses per

independent variable. This enables the performance of regression analyses, and the minimum probability level (p-value) was selected to be 0.05 [40].

Sampling procedures

Study participants were recruited through two non-probabilistic, purposive sampling techniques namely: venue-based and snowballing sampling. The recruited started with the venue-based wherein non-government organisations in states invited members of the target communities to participate in the study. Study participants who responded to the invitation met with field workers at designated venues and were provided with a weblink to the survey to enable them fill in the questionnaire independently and anonymously using phone, tablet, or computer-assisted self-interviewing. If the participant had literacy issues, the interviewer offered computer-assisted personal interviewing. The second wave of respondents were recruited through snowballing wherein participants who completed the survey were given coupons to up to five peers who may not have been connected to community organisations. Participants were also recruited through the online river sampling method in Enugu, Gombe and Niger states (the survey link was posted on Facebook, Twitter, Instagram and WhatsApp groups or email networks peers invited to take the survey).

Study procedures

Community entry was facilitated through the support of national networks of target populations. The networks were actively engaged with the study design, selection of target states for the recruitment of study participants, facilitated community entry and mobilisation of community members for the study. Details of the community engagement procedure for the primary study had been described in prior publications [11, 12, 39].

Field workers engaged with data collection were also trained on the study protocol, communication and ethical considerations for study conduct. Each field worker piloted the study questionnaire. Each field workers conducted a day training on the study protocol with two community entry representatives they worked with. Each community entry representative piloted the study questionnaire with a member of the target community. Prior to the piloting of the questionnaire by the field workers and community entry representatives, the content of the study tool was validated

by a multidisciplinary team of scientists, with attention given to the elaboration of questions, the selection of validated instruments and their relevance to the objectives of the survey. The questionnaire content was then harmonised with standard indicators and protocol checklists used in behavioural surveillance.

The data was collected electronically using the LimeSurvey™. The platform is a secure with SSL encrypted connection link. The link did not require any personal identifier, email, phone or person-to-person contact. Data in transit were encrypted using secure TLS cryptographic protocols. The collection tool had certified its compliance with the EU-U.S. Privacy Shield Framework (GDPR) and Swiss-U.S. Privacy Shield. It also did not install any targeting or advertising cookies. IP addresses were instantly decoupled from the questionnaire, encrypted, and deleted at the end of the online survey (6 weeks) by the survey tool.

The survey was administered in English. Keywords in the questionnaires were translated into Yoruba, Igbo, Hausa and specific dialects or local languages predominant in the states identified for the study. Translation of keywords and phrases into local dialects were made in consultation with community leaders participating in the project.

Study Independent Variables

Social vulnerability status: We identified the different status of the study participants through their response to a question asking about their vulnerability status. A tick of the checkbox against a vulnerability status as classified as a ‘yes’ response. Those who did not tick the box were classified as a ‘no’ response. The status identified were girls and young women with disability (yes/no), people on the move (yes/no), involved with transactional sex (yes/no), involved with sex work (yes/no) and use psychoactive substances (yes/no). The choice of these socially vulnerable groups to HIV infection was based on the Political Declaration to End HIV and End Inequality approved by the United Nations General Assembly in June 2021.

HIV status: The HIV status of participants was assessed with a question that asked in the participants know their HIV status. The response options were HIV negative, HIV positive, and

don't know or won't say. A tick of the checkbox against a vulnerability status as classified as a 'yes' response. Those who did not tick the box were classified as a 'no' response.

Study Dependent Variables

Psychological distress: The psychological distress status was measured using the Patient Health Questionnaire-4 (PHQ-4). This a 4-item inventory rated on a 4-point Likert-type scale. The instrument screens for depression and anxiety [41]. The tool had been validated for brief screening of self-reported depression and anxiety and had been used for assessment of psychological distress during the COVID-19 pandemic in Nigeria [42]. Each of the four items on the PHQ-4 is scored on a scale of 0 (not at all) to 3 (nearly every day). When the total score is greater than or equal to 3, a presumptive diagnosis of anxiety, depression, or both can be made [43]. By using a cut-off score of 3, we dichotomized the PHQ-4 into two groups: those with a score below 3, indicating no or low levels of anxiety and depression, and those with a score of 3 or higher, indicating a possible diagnosis of anxiety, depression, or both [43].

Suicidal ideation: We identified suicidal ideation with the question "In the past 6 months, how often have you thought about taking your own life?" (Never/seldom/very often/all the time). Respondents that who selected any of 'seldom', 'very often', or 'all the time' were considered to have suicide ideation.

Confounding Variables

Sociodemographic variables: Age of study participants (dichotomised into 15-18-years-old and 19-24-years-old), educational status (no formal/primary education, secondary/vocational education, and postsecondary/university education), and socioeconomic standing. The socioeconomic standing of participants was derived using a variable in which they were asked to rate themselves from on a scale of 1 -10, with 1 representing being among those "having the least money, least education and least respected jobs or no job", and 10 representing being "among those having most money, most education and most respected jobs" within the country. The rankings were converted to terciles representing lower, middle, and higher relative socioeconomic standing.

Data Management and Data Analysis

The research team monitored the situation of the online questionnaire as well as the response rate per country. Any respondent leaving the survey before completing a module is de facto excluded from the survey. Respondents choosing to click on the ‘exit’ button are also excluded from the survey. To increase the quality of the dataset, the research team constructed discrepancy flags which indicated whether respondents supplied inconsistent data in different areas of the questionnaire. Non-qualifiers were respondents who did not meet the criteria for inclusion in the study. These criteria were consent not provided, not providing a numeric value for age and not belonging to any of the study target populations.

We conducted a bivariate analysis to test the associations between the dependent and independent variables using Pearson’s chi-squared. A binary logistics regression model was built exploring the associations between the dependent and independent variables after adjusting for the confounders. Statistical significance was taken at p-value less than 0.05. Statistical analyses were performed using Stata 16.

Results

Table 1 showed the results of the bivariable analysis between the psychological distress, the independent variables, and the confounders. The data of 1,509 individuals were included in the analysis of whom 1147 (76.0%) had psychological distress. Disability status was not significantly associated with psychological distress ($p=0.309$). Participants who used psychoactive substances ($p<0.001$), engaged in sex work ($p<0.001$), were involved in transactional sex ($p<0.001$), were frequently on the move ($p=0.021$), or had a precarious living status ($p<0.001$) had a significantly higher likelihood of experiencing psychological distress.

Table 1: Test of associations between psychological distress, sociodemographic profile, vulnerability status and HIV status among adolescents and young women who are at high risk for HIV or living with HIV in Nigeria during the COVID-19 pandemic (N=1509)

Variables	Has psychological distress		Test of association
	No	Yes	
Age group			
15-18 (n=473)	136 (28.8)	337 (71.2)	$\chi^2=8.57$
19-24 (n=1,036)	226 (21.8)	810 (78.2)	$p=0.003$

Total (n=1,509)	362 (24.0)	1147 (76.0)	
Educational status			
No formal education/Primary (n=355)	94 (26.5)	261 (73.5)	$\chi^2=2.09$ $p=0.352$
Secondary/Vocational (n=815)	195 (23.9)	620 (76.1)	
Postsecondary/University (n=335)	73 (21.8)	262 (78.2)	
Total (n=1,505)	362 (24.1)	1,143 (75.9)	
Socioeconomic standing			
Lower (n=534)	80 (15)	454 (85)	$\chi^2=49.48$ $p<0.001$
Middle (n=643)	164 (25.5)	479 (74.5)	
Higher (n=327)	117 (35.8)	210 (64.2)	
Total (n=1,504)	361 (24)	1,143 (76)	
Living with disability			
No (n=1,390)	338 (24.3)	1,052 (75.7)	$\chi^2=1.03$ $p=0.309$
Yes (n=119)	24 (20.2)	95 (79.8)	
Total (n=1,509)	362 (24)	1,147 (76)	
Use psychoactive substances			
No (n=1,193)	323 (27.1)	870 (72.9)	$\chi^2=29.74$ $p<0.001$
Yes (n=316)	39 (12.3)	277 (87.7)	
Total (n=1,509)	362 (24)	1,147 (76)	
Involved in sex work			
No (n=917)	271 (29.6)	646 (70.4)	$\chi^2=39.6770$ $p<0.001$
Yes (n=592)	91 (15.4)	501 (84.6)	
Total (n=1,509)	362 (24)	1,147 (76)	
Involved in transactional sex			
No (n=797)	248 (31.1)	549 (68.9)	$\chi^2=47.06$ $p<0.001$
Yes (n=712)	114 (16)	598 (84)	
Total (n=1,509)	362 (24)	1,147 (76)	
People on the move			
No (n=1,156)	278 (24)	878 (76)	$\chi^2=5.32$ $p=0.021$
Yes (n=202)	64 (31.7)	138 (68.3)	
Total (n=1,358)	342 (25.2)	1,016 (74.8)	
HIV status			
HIV negative (n=595)	171 (28.7)	424 (71.3)	$\chi^2=68.34$ $p<0.001$
HIV positive (n=673)	98 (14.6)	575 (85.4)	
Don't know/Won't say (n=241)	93 (38.6)	148 (61.4)	
Total (n=1,509)	362 (24)	1,147 (76)	

Table 2 highlights the association between suicidal ideation, the independent variables and the confounders. The sample consists of 1,744 individuals, among whom 603 (34.7%) reported suicidal ideation. Disability status ($p=0.903$) and been on the move ($p=0.942$) w not significantly associated with suicidal ideation. Study participants who reported using psychoactive substances

($p < 0.001$), engaging in sex work ($p < 0.001$), engaging in transactional sex ($p < 0.001$), or living with HIV ($p = 0.007$) had a significantly higher incidence of suicidal ideation.

Table 2: Test of associations between suicidal ideation, sociodemographic profile, vulnerability status and HIV status among adolescents and young women who are at high risk for HIV or living with HIV in Nigeria during the COVID-19 pandemic (N=1735)

Variables	Suicide ideation		Test of association
	No	Yes	
Age group			
15-18 (n=571)	340 (59.5)	231 (40.5)	$\chi^2=12.97$ $p < 0.001$
19-24 (n=1,173)	801 (68.3)	372 (31.7)	
Total (n=1,744)	1141 (65.4)	603 (34.6)	
Educational status			
No formal education/Primary (n=445)	257 (57.8)	188 (42.2)	$\chi^2=15.27$ $p < 0.001$
Secondary/Vocational (n=930)	628 (67.5)	302 (32.5)	
Postsecondary/University (n=360)	248 (68.9)	112 (31.1)	
Total (n=1,735)	1133 (65.3)	602 (34.7)	
Socioeconomic standing			
Lower (n=625)	391 (62.6)	234 (37.4)	$\chi^2=9.21$ $p = 0.010$
Middle (n=714)	446 (62.5)	268 (37.5)	
Higher (n=351)	250 (71.2)	101 (28.8)	
Total (n=1,690)	1087 (64.3)	603 (35.7)	
Living with disability			
No (n=1,612)	1054 (65.4)	558 (34.6)	$\chi^2=0.01$ $p = 0.903$
Yes (n=132)	87 (65.9)	45 (34.1)	
Total (n=1,744)	1141 (65.4)	603 (34.6)	
Use psychoactive substances			
No (n=1,333)	914 (68.6)	419 (31.4)	$\chi^2=24.70$ $p < 0.001$
Yes (n=411)	227 (55.2)	184 (44.8)	
Total (n=1,744)	1141 (65.4)	603 (34.6)	
Involved in sex work			
No (n=1,040)	759 (73)	281 (27)	$\chi^2=65.0330$ $p < 0.001$
Yes (n=704)	382 (54.3)	322 (45.7)	
Total (n=1,744)	1141 (65.4)	603 (34.6)	
Involved in transactional sex			
No (n=910)	679 (74.6)	231 (25.4)	$\chi^2=71.06$ $p < 0.001$
Yes (n=834)	462 (55.4)	372 (44.6)	
Total (n=1,744)	1141 (65.4)	603 (34.6)	
People on the move			
No (n=1,311)	845 (64.5)	466 (35.5)	$\chi^2=0.01$ $p = 0.942$
Yes (n=221)	143 (64.7)	78 (35.3)	
Total (n=1,532)	988 (64.5)	544 (35.5)	
HIV status			$\chi^2=9.83$

HIV negative (n=648)	446 (68.8)	202 (31.2)	p=0.007
HIV positive (n=774)	487 (62.9)	287 (37.1)	
Don't know/Won't say (n=278)	164 (59)	114 (41)	
Total (n=1,700)	1097 (64.5)	603 (35.5)	

Table 3 highlights the results of the multivariable logistic regression analysis determining risk indicators for psychological distress. The logistic regression analysis resulted in a likelihood ratio chi-squared statistic of 171.47 ($p < 0.0001$). The pseudo-R-squared value of 0.1123 indicates that the model explains approximately 11.23% of the variance in the outcome.

People with disability (AOR: 2.06; 95% CI: 1.24 - 3.43; $p = 0.005$), those who used psychoactive substances (AOR: 1.89; 95% CI: 1.28 - 2.81; $p = 0.002$), those involved with sex work (AOR: 1.58; 95% CI: 1.05 - 2.40; $p = 0.03$), and those living with HIV when compared with HIV negative status (AOR: 2.04, 95% CI: 1.50 - 2.76; $p < 0.0001$) had significantly higher odds of having psychological distress. Transactional sex and mobility status were not statistically significant association with psychological distress.

Table 4 highlights the results of the multivariable logistic regression analysis determining risk indicators for suicidal ideation. The logistic regression analysis resulted in a likelihood ratio chi-squared statistic of 102.13 ($p < 0.0001$). The pseudo-R-squared value of 0.0519 indicates that the model explains approximately 5.19% of the variance in the outcome.

There were no significant associations between disability, mobility status, HIV positive status when compared with HIV negative status and suicidal ideation. On the other hand, individuals who used psychoactive (AOR: 1.44; 95% CI: 1.10 - 1.87; $p = 0.007$), involved in sex work (AOR: 1.50; 95% CI: 1.08 - 2.09; $p = 0.015$), involved in transactional sex (AOR: 1.45; 95% CI: 1.04 - 2.04; $p = 0.030$) and who reported "don't know" or "won't say" for their HIV status when compared with HIV negative individuals (AOR: 1.57; 95% CI: 1.12 - 2.19; $p = 0.008$) had significantly higher odds of suicidal ideation.

Table 4: Multivariable logistic regression analyses to identify the risk indicators for psychological stress and suicidal ideation among adolescents and young women who are at high risk for HIV or living with HIV in Nigeria during the COVID-19 pandemic

Variables	Psychological distress		Suicidal ideation	
	AOR (95% CI)	p-value	AOR (95% CI)	p-value
Age group				
15-18 years	1	-	1	-
19-24 years	1.06 (0.78-1.45)	0.703	0.74 (0.57-0.95)	0.02
Educational status				
No formal education/Primary	1		1	
Secondary/vocational	1.33 (0.94-1.88)	0.104	0.67 (0.51-0.88)	0.004
Postsecondary/University	1.83 (1.17-2.86)	0.008	0.78 (0.54-1.11)	0.169
Socioeconomic standing				
Lower	1		1	
Middle	0.50 (0.36-0.70)	<0.001	1.11 (0.86-1.42)	0.428
Higher	0.30 (0.21-0.44)	<0.001	0.75 (0.54-1.05)	0.090
Living with disability				
No	1		1	
Yes	2.06 (1.24-3.43)	0.005	1.20 (0.79-1.81)	0.397
Use psychoactive substances				
No	1		1	
Yes	1.89 (1.28-2.81)	0.002	1.44 (1.1-1.87)	0.007
Involved in sex work				
No	1		1	
Yes	1.58 (1.05-2.40)	0.03	1.50 (1.08-2.09)	0.015
Involved in transactional sex				
No	1		1	
Yes	1.43 (0.96-2.14)	0.081	1.45 (1.04-2.04)	0.030
Person on the move				
No	1		1	
Yes	0.74 (0.51-1.08)	0.118	0.87 (0.63-1.21)	0.411
HIV status				
HIV negative	1		1	
HIV positive	2.04 (1.5-2.76)	<0.001	1.23 (0.96-1.57)	0.098
Don't know/Won't say	0.80 (0.55-1.15)	0.232	1.57 (1.12-2.19)	0.008
Constant	2.02 (1.3-3.15)	0.002	0.47 (0.33-0.68)	<0.001

Discussion

The study findings suggests that adolescent girls and young women who are vulnerable to HIV or living with HIV in Nigeria are not homogenous; different populations of adolescent girls and

young women seem to have different risk for psychological distress and suicidal ideation. Adolescent girls and young women who use psychoactive substances and sex workers seem more likely to experience both psychological distress and suicidal ideation during the COVID-19 pandemic. Those with disability and those living with HIV seem more likely to experience psychological distress; while those involved with transactional sex and those who don't know/who won't say their HIV status seem more likely to experience suicidal ideation. Adolescent girls and young women who were on the move seem not to have a significant risk for either psychological distress or suicidal ideation. The study findings, therefore, partially supported the study hypothesis.

One of the strengths of the study is the recruitment of many vulnerable and hidden population of adolescents and young females. This allows for a robust analysis to generate evidence on the impact of COVID-19 on vulnerable sub-populations of adolescents and young persons. This evidence is also one of the very few evidence on the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on sub-populations of young people in sub-Saharan Africa. Though the COVID-19 pandemic had been declared over [44], lessons learnt about the differential impact of the pandemic on different populations of adolescents and young people can inform for the planning of future epidemics of the magnitude and type of COVID-19. The study also has come limitations. First, this is a cross-sectional study and thus, limits deductions on causal relationships between the study variables. In addition, the sample was a convenient sample limiting the generalisability of the results though the use of multiple recruitment strategies, and the on-ground support to recruit study participants minimised the risk of exclusion associated with online recruitment. Despite these limitations, our study findings raise a few pertinent issues discussed below.

First, the study demonstrates that not all vulnerable sub-populations of adolescent girls and young women may have been prone to psychological stress and suicidal ideation during the COVID-19 pandemic while some had worse impact. It seems those involved with sex work and those who use psychoactive substances had the worst effect being that the population seem to have high risk for psychological distress and suicidal ideation. Of concern is the higher likelihood of adolescents with mental health disorders like psychological distress, attempting suicide [45]. Adolescents and young persons access to illegal psychoactive substances is increasing [46] and the risk for suicidality with use of psychoactive substances due to impulsivity and loss of self-control is also

high [47]. Adolescence is also a period of heightened psychological stress due to the significant social, cognitive, and biological changes they go through [48]. Sex work as an adolescent and young person may also be associated with psychological stress, use of psychoactive substances and an increased risk for suicidal ideation. However, there is little clarity about how this proposed nexus between mental health, psychoactive substance use, and sex work may have occurred or may have been heightened during the pandemic. This needs further investigation.

Second, adolescent girls and young women involved with transactional sex and those who don't know/who won't say their HIV status seem more likely to experience suicidal ideation. However, though those involved with transactional sex had an increased though insignificant risk for psychological stress, those who don't know/who won't say their HIV status had a reduced though insignificant risk for suicidal ideation. These findings suggest that there may be pathways to suicidal ideation independent of psychological stress especially for those who don't know/who won't say their HIV status. A common trait between the two sub-populations may be shame. Involvement in transactional sex is for survival and not as work. The driver for transactional sex may be the cause of psychological stress (adolescent girls and young women who sell or transact sex seem to be work affected by the social and economic situation generated by COVID-19 pandemic [12]), while transactional sex and the stigma associated with sex work may be the driver for suicidal ideation. On the other hand, adolescents and young persons don't know/who won't say their HIV status may be in denial of their HIV status. Not being public about their HIV status may reduce the psychological stress but the shame of being HIV positive may drive suicidal ideation. An estimated 5% of adolescents who know their HIV positivity status live in denial of it in Nigeria [49] though a significantly large number of adolescents do not test for HIV for varied reasons including not willing to know their HIV status for fear of stigma if HIV positive [50]. Our postulation on the association between not knowing/not wanting to tell one's HIV status is related to adolescents who know they are HIV positive but live in denial of it. Further studies are needed to explore this postulation. Studies on HIV among adolescents in Nigeria should also include sub-populations of people who don't know/who won't say their HIV status as they seem to constitute a unique population with a different mental health risk from other sub-populations of adolescents and young persons.

Third, adolescent girls and young women with disability and those living with HIV seem more likely to experience psychological stress and faced no differential risk for suicidal ideation during the COVID-19 pandemic. Our prior study had suggested that people living with HIV may have lived a chronic life of psychological stress [ref] that makes them better adapted for the COVID-19 associated stress. We also add that this postulation may be stretched further to suggest that the adaptation may make people living with HIV less likely to engage with COVID-19 associated suicidal ideation. Concerns with contract COVID-19 and worsening financial vulnerability and food security due to the lockdown may have caused the psychological stress observed for both sub-populations [12]. Further studies are needed to understand how this sub-population of girls and women, despite their vulnerability did not experience an increase in risk for suicidal ideation during the COVID-19 pandemic. Similar studies are also needed to understand how adolescent girls and women on the move seem not to have experienced an elevated risk for psychological stress or suicidal ideation.

The study findings seem to suggest that the pathway of HIV vulnerable adolescents and young girls in Nigeria to psychological stress and suicidal ideation may not be limited to a vulnerability pathway. The pseudo-R-squared values for the multivariable logistic regression models seem to suggest that the vulnerability status was less of an explanatory variable for suicidal ideation than it was for psychological stress. From the study findings, we suggest that sub-populations of adolescent girls and young women living at high risk of HIV or living with HIV may have different exposures to stress factors during the COVID-19 pandemic that may affect their risk for psychological stress and suicidal ideation. Further studies are needed to identify these risk factors so that they can be ameliorated for every sub-population of HIV vulnerable adolescent girls and young women during future pandemics with the magnitude and impact of COVID-19.

In conclusion, we identified that the adolescent girls and young women who use psychoactive substances, who are involved with sex workers, those with disability and those living with HIV seem more likely to experience psychological distress than those who are not members of the sub-population. We suggest that the intensity of psychological distress experienced by adolescent girls and young women who use psychoactive substances and who are involved with sex workers that may have predisposed them to significantly high risk for suicidal ideation may not have been

experienced by those with disability and those living with HIV. The experience of shame and concern about stigma may have been the risk pathway for suicidal ideation for those involved with transactional sex and those who don't know/who won't say their HIV status. The shame and stigma pathway may moderate the risk for suicidal ideation with involving the psychological distress pathway. The protective pathway that reduces the risk of adolescent girls and women who are on the move to psychological distress or suicidal ideation when compared with their peers is not known. Further studies are needed to explore our study postulations.

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